

Geographically-enabled Agent-based Model for COVID-19 Transmission

Kaushik Ram Ganapathy
Halicioglu Data Science Institute
University of California San Diego
La Jolla, California, United States of America
krganapa@ucsd.edu

Bailey Man
Halicioglu Data Science Institute
University of California San Diego
La Jolla, California, United States of America
bmman@ucsd.edu

Jiayi Lei
Halicioglu Data Science Institute
University of California San Diego
La Jolla, California, United States of America
jil1119@ucsd.edu

Ilya Zaslavsky
San Diego Supercomputer Center
University of California San Diego
La Jolla, California, United States of America
zaslavsk@sdsc.edu

ABSTRACT

Geographically-enabled Agent-based model for COVID-19 Transmission (GeoACT) is a new science gateway developed to assist K-12 schools in evaluating potential strategies for safe school reopening amid the COVID-19 pandemic. School closures have resulted in learning interruptions, increased inequality and adverse economic impacts, and additional challenges to the social and intellectual development of students. Reopening schools for in-person instruction requires careful planning to avoid serious risks of infection especially with the rise of the more infectious virus variants. The core component of the gateway is an agent-based model simulating viral transmission in the course of daily school activities, under several intervention strategies. The model follows a modified SEIR approach, describing transitions between Susceptible, Exposed, Infected (symptomatic and asymptomatic), and Removed/Quarantined states for student and staff agents. A distinct feature of the model is that risks of viral exposure through both aerosol¹ and droplet transmission² are modeled for granularly-defined school activities (learning at desks, group activities, recess, lunch, etc.), which are simulated at 5-min intervals in specific spatial settings. The latter are extracted from school floor plans, including dimensions of classrooms and other school areas, their occupancy, and ventilation characteristics. The model is deployed on the XSEDE Expanse resource and accessed via the Apache Airavata³ portal. Users

can enter school-specific parameters, such as the number of employees and students in each grade, non-pharmaceutical interventions (NPIs) like mask-wearing, improved ventilation, and cohort separation; and pharmaceutical measures, namely vaccination levels, and testing strategies. An additional module simulates viral transmission on school buses, given different bus types, seating patterns, mask compliance, and whether windows and hatches are open or closed. Model runs generate risk heat maps and histograms that visually demonstrate the impact of the chosen intervention strategies. The preliminary results for selected elementary schools and bus routes showed that efficient reopening plans rely on a combination of mitigation strategies, most importantly minimizing cohort sizes, improving ventilation in enclosed spaces, and maximizing mask-wearing compliance.

Model results have been validated against outcomes of similar models^{4,5} and infection patterns reported in literature^{6,7}. Empirical model validation is pursued through our ongoing work with the San Diego County Office of Education (SDCOE) on generating and tracking school exposure notifications. Additional ongoing work focuses on improving model performance (in particular, switching to Julia and the Agents.jl⁸ framework from Python with MESA⁹ and MESA-GEO packages we used earlier), modeling additional school activities such as athletics,

integration with a spatial analysis dashboard, and developing a meta-analysis module on the Airavata portal.

We wish to acknowledge guidance and collaboration from San Diego County Health and Human Services Agency, SDCOE, and San Diego Unified School District, as well as support from XSEDE and the Science Gateways Community Institute (SGCI). NSF support (award 2139740) is gratefully acknowledged.

Keywords-- COVID-19, School Reopening, Agent-based Model, Gateway, Simulation, Transmission

REFERENCES

1. Bazant, Martin Z., and John WM Bush. "A guideline to limit indoor airborne transmission of COVID-19." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 118, no. 17 (2021).
2. Chen, Wenzhao, Nan Zhang, Jianjian Wei, Hui-Ling Yen, and Yuguo Li. "Short-range airborne route dominates exposure of respiratory infection during close contact." *Building and Environment* 176 (2020): 106859.
3. Marru, Suresh, Lahiru Gunathilake, Chathura Herath, Patanachai Tangchaisin, Marlon Pierce, Chris Mattmann, Raminder Singh et al. "Apache airavata: a framework for distributed applications and computational workflows." In *Proceedings of the 2011 ACM workshop on Gateway computing environments*, pp. 21-28. 2011.
4. Kerr, Cliff C., Robyn M. Stuart, Dina Mistry, Romesh G. Abeysuriya, Katherine Rosenfeld, Gregory R. Hart, Rafael C. Núñez et al. "Covasim: an agent-based model of COVID-19 dynamics and interventions." *PLOS Computational Biology* 17, no. 7 (2021): e1009149.
5. Bilinski, Alyssa, Joshua A. Salomon, John Giardina, Andrea Ciaranello, and Meagan C. Fitzpatrick. "Passing the test: a model-based analysis of safe school-reopening strategies." *Annals of Internal Medicine* (2021).
6. Han, Xuejiao, Xuemei Li, Yinan Xiao, Ruoning Yang, Yang Wang, and Xiawei Wei. "Distinct characteristics of COVID-19 infection in children." *Frontiers in Pediatrics* 9 (2021): 130.
7. Sah, Pratha, Meagan C. Fitzpatrick, Charlotte F. Zimmer, Elaheh Abdollahi, Lyndon Juden-Kelly, Seyed M. Moghadas, Burton H. Singer, and Alison P. Galvani. "Asymptomatic SARS-CoV-2 infection: A systematic review and meta-analysis." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 118, no. 34 (2021).
8. Vahdati, Ali R. "Agents. jl: agent-based modeling framework in Julia." *Journal of Open Source Software* 4, no. 42 (2019): 1611.
9. Masad, David, and Jacqueline Kazil. "MESA: an agent-based modeling framework." In *14th PYTHON in Science Conference*, vol. 2015, pp. 53-60. 2015.